

KNOWLEDGE, PERCEPTIONS, AND REGULATORY ATTITUDES REGARDING NICOTINE POUCHES AMONG MALE COLLEGE STUDENTS IN SWAT, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Nicotine pouches are a rapidly emerging class of oral nicotine products promoted as smoke-free alternatives to cigarettes and traditional smokeless tobacco. Their increasing availability, especially through social media—has raised concerns about youth uptake and misinformation. In Pakistan, little is known about young people's awareness and perceptions of these products. This study evaluated knowledge, perceptions, and regulatory attitudes toward nicotine pouches among male college students in Swat and compared responses between government and private colleges.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted from August to October 2025 among 309 male intermediate students (≥ 18 years) from four colleges in Swat District. Participants completed a structured, self-administered questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were used to assess differences between government and private colleges ($p < 0.05$).

Results: Awareness of nicotine pouches was significantly higher among private-college students (89.6%) compared with government-college students (15.5%). Private-college students demonstrated better knowledge of product composition and use, while misconceptions about tobacco content and uncertainty regarding addictiveness were common in government colleges ($p < 0.001$). Private-college students were more likely to view nicotine pouches as less harmful and fashionable, with social media and peers as primary information sources. Despite varying perceptions, more than 90% of all participants supported health warnings, age restrictions, and educational measures.

Conclusion: Awareness and perceptions of nicotine pouches differ markedly between government and private college students in Swat, with higher exposure and more favourable views among private college students. Despite awareness of addictive potential, supportive attitudes persist, highlighting the need for targeted education and strengthened regulatory measures to protect youth from nicotine dependence.

INTRODUCTION

Tobacco use remains one of the foremost causes of preventable disease and death globally, accounting for more than 8 million deaths each year¹. In recent years, the tobacco and nicotine market has undergone substantial change with the emergence of novel nicotine products, including nicotine pouches, which deliver nicotine without tobacco leaf or combustion². Unlike traditional smokeless tobacco products such as snus, nicotine pouches typically contain pharmaceutical-grade nicotine, flavoring agents, and plant-derived fibers, and are promoted as smoke-free, discreet alternatives to cigarettes³. Since their commercial launch in Scandinavia in the early 2010s, these products have rapidly penetrated markets in North America, Europe, and Asia⁴.

The rapid growth of nicotine pouch use has raised important public health concerns, particularly regarding uptake among adolescents and young adults⁵. Evidence indicates that intensive marketing campaigns, diverse flavor varieties, and widespread social media promotion have contributed to heightened awareness and experimentation among youth⁶. Studies from the United States indicate that oral nicotine pouches have become increasingly popular among college students, with ever use reported among approximately 11–15% of students and higher prevalence observed in certain subgroups, raising concerns about nicotine exposure and addiction⁷. As nicotine pouches can deliver nicotine doses comparable to, or exceeding, those of cigarettes, they carry a significant risk of dependence, with associated sympathetic cardiovascular effects and neuroadaptations in reward pathways, especially in younger and nicotine-pouch users⁸.

In Pakistan, tobacco use remains a major public health concern, with approximately 19.1% of adults currently using tobacco products. While cigarette smoking and traditional forms of smokeless tobacco have been extensively studied, evidence regarding emerging nicotine products such as nicotine pouches remains limited^{9,10}. Understanding young people's knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes toward these products is essential for informing regulatory policies and preventive interventions. Accordingly, this study aimed to assess knowledge, perceptions, and regulatory attitudes

regarding nicotine pouches among male college students in Swat, Pakistan, and to compare these outcomes between students attending government and private colleges.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted among college students in Swat. The sample size was determined using the OpenEpi calculator. Based on an estimated population of 1,000 male intermediate students aged 18 years or older across four colleges, with a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and an assumed 50% prevalence of awareness regarding nicotine pouches, the minimum required sample size was calculated as 278. To account for a potential 10% non-response rate, the final target sample size was set at 309 participants. Students were recruited through convenience sampling. Formal approval was obtained from the respective college administrations.

Eligible participants included male students aged 18 years or above enrolled in intermediate programs at the selected colleges. Students younger than 18, those enrolled in non-intermediate programs, or those studying at institutions not included in the sampling frame were excluded. Data were collected from August to October 2025 using a structured, self-administered questionnaire available in both Urdu and English, following written informed consent.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages for categorical variables; means and standard deviations for continuous variables) were computed. The chi-square test of independence was used to examine associations between categorical variables, particularly comparing responses between government and private college students. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 309 college students participated in the study, including 155 from government colleges and 154 from private colleges. Most respondents were aged 18–20 years (65.4%), followed by 21–25 years (30.1%), with only 4.5% older than 25 years. Overall, 45.3% were enrolled in the pre-medical stream, 34.6% in pre-engineering, and 20.1% in arts. Just over half

of the students were in the first academic year (54.4%), while 45.6% were in the second year. A family history of smoking was reported by 37.9%

of participants, whereas 62.1% indicated that no one in their family smoked, as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of participants

Variable	Category	Government colleges n (%)	Private colleges n (%)
Age group	18–20 years	98 (63.2)	104 (67.5)
	21–25 years	50 (32.3)	43 (27.9)
	>25 years	7 (4.5)	7 (4.6)
Academic stream	Pre-medical	68 (43.9)	72 (46.8)
	Pre-engineering	55 (35.5)	52 (33.8)
	Arts	32 (20.6)	30 (19.4)
Academic year	1st year	85 (54.8)	83 (53.9)
	2nd year	70 (45.2)	71 (46.1)
Family history of smoking	Yes	58 (37.4)	59 (38.3)
	No	97 (62.6)	95 (61.7)

Knowledge and awareness of nicotine pouches differed substantially by college type. Only 15.5% of students from government colleges reported having heard of nicotine pouches, compared with 89.6% of students from private colleges. Government-college students most commonly described nicotine pouches as a tobacco product (55.5%), whereas the majority of private-college students identified them as a nicotine-only product (85.7%). Similar patterns were observed for knowledge of the method of use: 87.0% of private-college students stated that nicotine pouches are placed under the lip or gum, compared with 20.6% of government-college students, among whom 72.3% reported that they did not know how they are used.

Misconceptions about product content were also prominent: 74.8% of government-college students believed nicotine pouches contain tobacco, whereas 81.8% of private-college students believed they do not. In terms of perceived addictiveness, 85.1% of private-college students thought that nicotine pouches can cause addiction, compared with 33.5% of government-college students, among whom over half (56.8%) were unsure. Chi-square tests showed statistically significant differences between government and private colleges for all knowledge and awareness items (all $p < 0.001$), as shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Participants' knowledge and awareness regarding nicotine pouches

Variable	Response category	Government colleges n (%)	Private colleges n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Ever heard of nicotine pouches.	Yes	24 (15.5)	138 (89.6)	171.42	<0.001
	No	95 (61.3)	11 (7.1)		
	Not Sure	36 (23.2)	5 (3.2)		
Perceived nature of nicotine pouches	Tobacco product	86 (55.5)	18 (11.7)	182.15	<0.001
	Herbal product	10 (6.4)	3 (1.9)		
	Nicotine-only product	14 (9.0)	132 (85.7)		
	Don't know	45 (29.1)	1 (0.7)		

Perceived method of using nicotine pouches	Placed under the lip/gum	32 (20.6)	134 (87.0)	158.42	<0.001
	Chewed like gum	6 (3.9)	5 (3.2)		
	Smoked like a cigarette	3 (1.9)	4 (2.6)		
	Snorted like powder	2 (1.3)	3 (2.0)		
	Don't know	112 (72.3)	8 (5.2)		
Belief that nicotine pouches contain tobacco	Yes	116 (74.8)	22 (14.3)	120.84	<0.001
	No	12 (7.7)	126 (81.8)		
	Not Sure	27 (17.5)	6 (3.9)		
Belief that nicotine pouches can cause addiction	Yes	52 (33.5)	131 (85.1)	85.62	<0.001
	No	15 (9.7)	3 (1.9)		
	Not Sure	88 (56.8)	20 (13.0)		

Perceptions of harm relative to cigarettes and sources of information also varied significantly by institution type. Among government-college students, 61.3% reported that they did not know whether nicotine pouches are more or less harmful than cigarettes, whereas two-thirds (66.2%) of private-college students considered them less harmful. Only small proportions in either group believed that nicotine pouches are

more harmful than cigarettes. With respect to sources of awareness, most government-college students (61.3%) reported that they had never heard of nicotine pouches, while private-college students most commonly cited social media (44.2%) and friends (35.1%) as their primary sources. These differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), as shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Perceived harm and sources of awareness regarding nicotine pouches

Variable	Category	Government colleges n (%)	Private colleges n (%)	p-value
Perceived harm of nicotine pouches vs. cigarettes	More harmful	12 (7.7)	14 (9.1)	<0.001
	Less harmful	18 (11.6)	102 (66.2)	
	Equally harmful	30 (19.4)	27 (17.5)	
	Don't know	95 (61.3)	11 (7.2)	
Primary source of information about nicotine pouches	Friends	18 (11.6)	54 (35.1)	<0.001
	Social media	14 (9.0)	68 (44.2)	
	Advertisement	2 (1.3)	12 (7.8)	
	Family/college	26 (16.8)	9 (5.8)	
	Never heard	95 (61.3)	11 (7.1)	

Behavioral perceptions toward nicotine pouches were also more favorable among private-college students than among students from government colleges. While the majority of government-college students remained neutral (58.7%) and 33.6% disagreed (disagree 20.6%, Strongly disagree 13%) with the statement that nicotine pouches are safer than cigarettes, 59.7% (agree 39%, Strongly agree 20.7%) of private-college

students agreed or strongly agreed with this statement. Similarly, 70.1% (agree 57.1%, strongly agree 13%) of private-college students agreed or strongly agreed that using nicotine pouches is a fashionable trend, compared with only 15.6% of government-college students, among whom most either disagreed (40.0%) or strongly disagreed (19.4%). These differences in behavioral perceptions were statistically

significant (both $p < 0.001$), as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Behavioral perceptions regarding nicotine pouches

Variable	Response	Government colleges n (%)	Private colleges n (%)	p-value
Agreement that nicotine pouches are safer than cigarettes	Strongly agree	5 (3.2)	60 (39.0)	<0.001
	Agree	7 (4.5)	32 (20.7)	
	Neutral	91 (58.7)	48 (31.2)	
	Disagree	32 (20.6)	10 (6.5)	
	Strongly disagree	20 (13.0)	4 (2.6)	
Agreement that using nicotine pouches is a fashionable trend	Strongly agree	8 (5.2)	88 (57.1)	<0.001
	Agree	16 (10.4)	20 (13.0)	
	Neutral	45 (29.0)	31 (20.1)	
	Disagree	62 (40.0)	10 (6.5)	
	Strongly disagree	30 (19.4)	5 (3.3)	

Despite varying levels of awareness and perceptions, there was broad support for regulatory measures related to nicotine pouches among the overall sample. Across all participants, 91.3% (65.4% strongly agree, 25.9% agree) supported the inclusion of health warnings on nicotine pouch products, and

94.5% (72.1% strongly agree, 22.4% agree) favored a ban on the sale of nicotine pouches to minors. Similarly, 89.6% (60.2% strongly agree, 29.4% agree) agreed that education about the risks of nicotine pouches is necessary, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Attitudes toward the regulation of nicotine pouches

Variable	Health warnings on nicotine pouch packaging, %	Ban on sale of nicotine pouches to minors, %	Education about the risks of nicotine pouches, %
Strongly agree	65.4	72.1	60.2
Agree	25.9	22.4	29.4
Neutral	5.5	3.2	6.8
Disagree	2.0	1.5	2.1
Strongly disagree	1.2	0.8	1.5

DISCUSSION

This study highlights a significant difference in awareness of nicotine pouches between students enrolled in government and private colleges in Swat, Pakistan. Only 15.5% of students from government colleges reported having prior knowledge, whereas awareness was substantially higher at 89.6% among students from private colleges. This difference is considerably greater than the levels of awareness documented in

comparable regional studies, including research among Saudi medical students, where awareness was reported at 58.6%, and a study conducted in Karachi that found a rate of 61.8%. This contrast points to a substantial informational imbalance, likely influenced by differences in access to digital resources and underlying socioeconomic conditions^{11,12}. Evidence from other low- and middle-income settings similarly indicates that individuals from lower

socioeconomic backgrounds face greater vulnerability to tobacco use while also having limited access to health-related information. These findings suggest that broader structural determinants play a central role in shaping this educational gap¹³. As a result, the primary sources of awareness varied substantially between groups. Among private college students, social media platforms (44.2%) and friends' networks (35.1%) were the most frequently reported channels of information, reflecting global evidence that online exposure and peer influence are major contributors to the uptake of emerging nicotine products^{11,14}. This situation is further intensified by reports of aggressive marketing practices and the widespread availability of nicotine pouches at retail outlets across Pakistan, creating an information landscape for more advantaged youth that is shaped largely by commercial and social forces rather than formal public health communication¹⁵.

However, higher awareness among private college students did not correspond with an accurate understanding of the associated risks. Instead, it was linked to concerning perceptions that these products are relatively harmless. Two-thirds of students (66.2%) perceived nicotine pouches as less harmful than cigarettes, and 59.7% considered them safer, while a majority also regarded them as fashionable (70.1%). This indicates that exposure frequently via marketing narratives highlighting modernity and reduced harm can normalize use without effectively communicating the risks of nicotine dependence^{11,16}. Interestingly, 85.1% of private college students acknowledged the addictive potential of these products, indicating a cognitive disconnect in which awareness of risk exists alongside continued behavioral appeal, a pattern also observed in studies of youth substance use¹⁷. In sharp contrast, most government college students showed a notable lack of information, with 61.3% uncertain about the relative harm and 56.8% unsure about addictiveness, leaving them particularly susceptible to future misinformation¹¹. Misconceptions regarding product content were also prevalent, with 74.8% of government students incorrectly believing that nicotine pouches contain tobacco, while 81.8% of private students correctly recognized them as tobacco-

free. This distinction is important, as the "tobacco-free" label may be mistakenly interpreted as implying "risk-free," potentially obscuring the dangers of nicotine dependence¹⁶. Despite these differences in knowledge and perceptions, there was a strong and consistent consensus in favor of stricter regulation. More than 90% of participants supported health warnings, 94.5% advocated for a ban on sales to minors, and 89.6% endorsed educational initiatives. This widespread agreement highlights a clear mandate for policymakers to address the current regulatory gaps surrounding novel nicotine products in Pakistan^{15,16,18}. The findings highlight an urgent need for targeted, equity-oriented interventions. For students in government colleges, basic education on the nature of nicotine pouches and their associated risks is critical. For students in private colleges, programs should emphasize media literacy to critically evaluate marketing messages and address the disconnect between awareness of addictive potential and perceptions of safety. These educational strategies should be complemented by comprehensive policy measures, including marketing restrictions, strict enforcement of age-of-sale laws, and prominent health warnings, all of which were strongly supported by the study participants^{15,18}. This study indicates that without timely intervention, the current patterns of awareness, largely shaped by unregulated commercial and social channels, may contribute to the normalization of nicotine pouch use and exacerbate existing health inequalities. The findings underscore the need for targeted educational programs and comprehensive policy measures to address knowledge gaps. Implementing proactive strategies is essential to prevent a new wave of nicotine addiction among young people and to provide a preventive framework applicable to similar contexts globally.

LIMITATIONS

This study was conducted among male students in a single district, which limits the generalizability of the findings. Its cross-sectional design also prevents any causal inferences regarding awareness, perceptions, or behaviour's. Future research using longitudinal designs is necessary to track usage patterns over

time and evaluate the impact of policy interventions.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights clear differences in awareness and perceptions of nicotine pouches among male college students in Swat, Pakistan. Students in private colleges show higher awareness and more favorable perceptions, largely driven by peer influence and social media, while limited knowledge among government college students reflects a critical information gap and potential vulnerability to future marketing. Awareness of addictive potential does not consistently translate into cautious attitudes, indicating that social influences often outweigh health knowledge. Strong support for age restrictions, health warnings, and educational initiatives highlights the need for timely regulatory action to prevent the normalization of nicotine pouch use and reduce the risk of nicotine dependence among young people.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing interests, financial or otherwise, related to the current work.

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